

Study the Seroclearance of HBs Antigen in Patients with Confirmed Hepatitis B Infection During Receiving nucleotide Analogue in Comparison with No Treatment

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Abstract

Chronic HBV infection is defined as persistence of hepatitis B surface Antigen (HBSAg) for at least six months, and the testing strategy involves an initial serological test to detect HbsAg followed by HBV DNA viral load to help guide treatment decision. After recovery from acute HBV infection, the levels of HbsAg become undetectable. HbsAg concentrations differ during the varying longitudinal phases of disease and are generally higher in individuals with detectable HbeAg. With the development of novel antiviral agents to treat CHB, there has been renewed interest in using HbsAg loss as a therapeutic endpoint and predict the seroclearance. A total of 40 samples were collected from patients infected with Hbs viral infection who are outpatients to Abu Ghraib General Hospital, Baghdad and Al-Qaim General Hospital in Al-Qaim city and Fallujah Teaching hospital for maternity and children and Many private laboratories in Fallujah city from 15th October 2022 to 2nd March 2023. The included patients in this study were patients who are infected with Hepatitis B (Hbs)Virus infection from different stages of infection (especially the end stage of infection) or recovered from the infection. A questionnaire was applied during sample collection to gather the information from patients including: age, Gender, Type of drug, Stage of disease, Time from infection, HBS viral load if present, liver enzymes (ALT, AST, ALP) if present. Many of those information were excluded because of its none availability for many patients. One of the most important stages that any patient infected with HBs virus aim to reach it is the seroclearance stage when he would be eligible to practice his activities normally as a carrier for the infection. Therefore; this study aims to study the patient characteristics that might be correlate with attaining the seroclearance state including the age, gender, disease stage and specifically the type of drug. The study results showed that among 30 patients randomly selected with confirmed HBs infection recently, the number of Males (19) is higher than Females (11) and the concentration of

More Information

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HBs Ag is higher in the males (15.170 ± 6.51 ng/ml) than females (14.40 ± 7.66 ng/ml) with no significant differences calculated statistically (P value > 0.05). The mean of ages in our study was 41.8 ± 13.4 years and the percentage of ages higher than 35 years (30%) was lower than younger patients under 35 years (70%) indicating that most of infected people were younger age groups from our population. The concentrations of HBs Ag in the patients older than 35 years were lower significantly (15.0 ± 6.9 ng/ml; P value = 0.02) than the patients younger than 35 years (15.5 ± 6.9 ng/ml) without presence of significant correlation between ages and gender (P value = 0.282). Most of the patients that included in our study were patients with end or advanced stage of infection who may receive drug for treatment of not (93.3 %) with a mean ($14.95142857 \pm 6.896200152$ ng/ml) compared with those who were in the initial stages of therapy who represent a low percentage of our study group (6.6 %) with a mean (19.125 ± 0.005 ng/ml). Most of the patients who were in the end stage of infection were in the age group older than 35 years (20) and lesser numbers exist in the age group younger than 35 years (8). Only 4 patients in our study showed undetectable concentrations of HBs Ag while the highest number (significantly with a P value = 0.03) of the patients showed positive results ranging from (8.08 ng/ml to 20.47 ng/ml) with a mean equal to 17.57 ± 3.4 ng/ml. The highest number of patients in our study did not receive any type of treatment during the period of sample collection (with no confirmation if they receive any drug recently or not) were 13 patients followed by Tenofovir and Entecavir (7 and 6 sequentially) and the least number were patients who receive adefovir (3 patients) followed by lamivudine (1 patient only).

Introduction

Hepatitis B Virus Structure and Life Cycle:

Hepatitis B virus (HBV) is an enveloped DNA virus, [1] that belongs to the *Hepadnaviridae* family [23]. The envelope surrounds an icosahedral nucleocapsid, which encloses a partially double-stranded, relaxed circular DNA (rcDNA) genome of ~3.2 kilobases. Four partially overlapping open reading frames (ORFs), termed P (polymerase), S (surface), C (core) and X (HBx protein), define the coding capacity of the HBV genome.

Phylogenetic analyses of HBV strains isolated from various regions of the world have identified ten major genotypes (A–J) that differ at the nucleotide level across full-length genomes by $>8\%$ [2].

At least three types of HBV particles are observed in the serum of infected patients: spherical structures of 42 nm in diameter, those with a diameter of 22 nm, and filament structures of variable length that are 22 nm in a diameter (Figure. 1; [3]).

Figure 1: A. Schematic representation of HBV particles. Infectious HBV virion (Dane particle) (upper) and non-infectious HBV particles, including enveloped capsids containing immature DNA/RNA, subviral particles (sphere and filament), and naked nucleocapsids (lower). B. Electron micrograph of HBs

Source: [3]

The 42 nm particles, also called Dane particles, are infectious virions consisting of a lipid membrane with three viral surface antigens (HBs), large (L-HBs), middle (M-HBs), and small (S-HBs), that surround a nucleocapsid composed of hepatitis B core protein (HBc), viral polymerase (Pol), and viral genome DNA [3].

The 22 nm particles, which are much more abundant in patient serum, include subviral particles (SVPs) that lack the nucleocapsid and are thus non-infectious. Also, other non-infectious particles are currently known to be produced by infection, including enveloped particles

that lack a viral genome, those containing viral RNA, and envelope-less particles (naked nucleocapsids) [4]. The HBV genome DNA is a relaxed-circular DNA (rcDNA). The produced HBc protein product initially associates to yield assembles into an icosahedral capsid consisting of 90 or 120 dimers, which incorporates the 3.5 Kb viral pregenomic RNA (pgRNA) associated with Pol. Pol is the largest HBV protein, consisting of four domains [3]. HBx is a multifunctional protein that promotes viral production at multiple steps, including viral transcription and replication, and also plays a role in the development of HBV-related hepatocellular carcinoma. HBV proliferates in host cells by taking advantage of these viral proteins in concert with host-derived factors [5].

HBV entry into host hepatocytes follows multiple steps. Initially, the virus attaches to the host cell surface through binding to factors including heparan sulfate proteoglycans (HSPGs) such as glypican 5 in a non-specific and low-affinity manner, and then interacts with its receptor(s) more specifically and with high affinity [6].

Sodium taurocholate cotransporting peptide (NTCP/SLC10A1), which is specifically expressed in the liver and originally functions to uptake bile salts into hepatocytes, was identified as an HBV and HDV entry receptor in 2012 [3]. Virus-receptor interactions are believed to trigger virus internalization into cells in an endocytosis-dependent manner [7,8]. In the nucleus, HBV genomic DNA is modified by cellular factors [3]. Following entry, the rcDNA genome is transported into the nucleus and converted into covalently closed circular DNA (cccDNA) using the host cell DNA repair response [9].

HBV cccDNA molecules associate with histones H3 and H4 and non-histone proteins, forming a typical viral minichromosome [2]; where the gaps in both plus and minus strands are filled and ligated to generate cccDNA [3]. Several factors have been reported to be involved in the process of cccDNA formation. A DNA repair enzyme, tyrosyl-DNA phosphodiesterase 2 (TDP2), has been shown to cleave the tyrosyl-DNA phosphodiester bond between Pol and rcDNA in an in vitro assay, although its relevance in cccDNA formation in the cellular context remains controversial. Although it remains unknown how and where cccDNA is maintained in the nucleus, cccDNA is inherently stable, which thus functions as a template for viral replication over the long term. A recent analysis showed a cccDNA half-life of about 40 days in NTCP-overexpressing HepG2 cells [10].

But that in a clinical setting is likely to be far longer. A report estimated more than 9 months for a cccDNA half-life in hepatitis B patients [11].

Pregenomic RNA (pgRNA) is exported from the nucleus and forms the template for reverse transcription from which the two strands of HBV DNA are formed. The

pgRNA also serves as the translational template for the core protein and polymerase. Double-stranded linear HBV genomes are efficient precursors for HBV DNA integration into the host cell genome [12]). The production of double-stranded linear DNA increases with the progression of liver disease which corresponds to viral integration being a tumorigenic event. As HBV DNA integration typically leaves only the whole HBsAg ORF intact, this has implications for achieving therapeutic HBsAg loss [2].

Fig. 3. Schematic overview of the HBV life cycle. See the main text for a precise description of the HBV life cycle.

Figure 2: Schematic overview of the HBV life cycle. See the main text for a precise description of the HBV life cycle
Source: [3]

Hepatitis B Pathophysiology

HBV is transmitted by perinatal, percutaneous, and sexual exposure and by close person-to-person contact (presumably by open cuts and sores, especially among children in hyperendemic areas [13]). HBV infects and replicates largely in hepatocytes. Initiation of infection is a multistep process and involves the binding of a highly conformational determinant region (a) of the HBsAg glycoprotein to heparan sulfate proteoglycans on the cell surface [14]; this is a low-affinity binding reaction that is reversible. Subsequently, HBV interacts with its specific major receptor, the hepatic bile acid transporter sodium taurocholate co-transporting polypeptide (NTCP) [26], with high affinity via the large HBsAg (L) protein of the virus, triggering viral internalization [2].

A characteristic feature of HBV replication is the secretion into the blood of a vast excess of subviral particles of HBsAg, predominantly in the form of 17–25 nm enveloped spherical vesicles. In addition, the translation of the precore ORF can result in the presence of a secretory protein required for the establishment of chronicity, hepatitis B e antigen

(HBeAg; produced by processing of precore protein), in the serum during certain infection phases [9].

Chronic HBV infection can be considered a disease that is characterized by the failure to mount an effective and coordinated adaptive immune response, resulting in viral persistence, which may be a consequence of the ability of HBV to manipulate key innate immune responses. Coordinated innate and adaptive immune responses are important for clearance of HBV from the liver. Importantly, under most circumstances, HBV is noncytopathic (does not directly kill hepatocytes); thus, the liver inflammation and fibrosis that complicate long-term chronic infection are predominantly mediated by the host immune response [2].

Following HBV infection, there is a lag period of 4–7 weeks before HBV DNA and HBsAg become detectable in serum or the liver (incubation period). Gene array studies during the incubation period have not revealed a strong interferon-stimulated gene response, leading to the proposition that HBV might be a stealth virus capable of evading initial innate immuneresponses [15]. In addition, virus-driven suppressive responses have been demonstrated, including: blocking recruitment of natural killer (NK) cells, NK T cells and macrophages; decreasing cytokine secretion (interferon- γ (IFN γ), tumour necrosis factor (TNF), IL-6, IL-8 and IL-1 β) from Kupffer cells³⁸; and inhibition of Toll-like receptor (TLR)-signalling, within the hepatocyte [16].

In acute infection in adults, once viraemia becomes detectable, the HBV DNA level increases exponentially in serum to peak levels of 10^8 – 10^9 viralcopies per ml but then typically declines, preceding the onset of clinical hepatitis⁴¹. Peripheral HBV-specific CD4+ and CD8+ T cell-mediated responses become detectable with the exponential increase in HBV replication. In the liver, there is a lack of any detectable cellular infiltration of immune cells, suggesting a process of noncytolytic (no direct killing of infected hepatocytes) clearance of HBV, which mainly involves cytokine-mediated inhibition of HBV replication via IFN γ and TNF, which are secreted from virus-specific CD8+ T cells⁴². The clearance of infected hepatocytes and prevention of further intrahepatic spread probably require a combination of cytolytic and noncytolytic mechanisms⁴³. Thus, during acute resolving hepatitis B, there is a robust, coordinated adaptive immune response with virus-specific CD8+ T cells mediating clearance of infected cells, B cells secreting neutralizing antibodies against HBsAg (anti-HBs) that block further infection and CD4+ T cells supporting effective viral clearance⁴⁴. Importantly, acute hepatitis B with full clinical recovery does not usually occur when the infection occurs perinatally and in very early childhood because of the immaturity of the immune system, which can lead to chronic infection [2].

Persistent chronic HBV infection occurs mainly in infections acquired at birth or during the first 2 years of life. Virological factors that can influence persistence include the continuous production of HBsAg in concentrations at least 1,000-fold higher than that of infectious virions [17].

Notably, in chronic HBV infection, the frequency and function of both intrahepatic and peripheral HBV-specific T cells are inversely proportional to the level of circulating HBV DNA [2].

On average, ~25% of untreated individuals with chronic HBV infection will die of cirrhosis complications and/or HCC; this number increases to 50% if only men are taken into account. However, there is a lack of recent studies on the natural history of untreated HBV infection, as it is unethical to deny treatment for the virus. The incidence of long-term sequelae of hepatitis B, which are cirrhosis and HCC, generally parallels the occurrence of chronic HBV infection [9].

The incidence of the cirrhosis and HCC can be difficult to assess owing to the slow evolution of disease from chronic hepatitis to cirrhosis and HCC. Furthermore, cirrhosis and HCC are asymptomatic in the early stage and currently lack good noninvasive biomarkers, making diagnosis difficult [2]. According to the WHO, mortality due to viral hepatitis is increasing [18]

Chronic HBV infection progresses to cirrhosis in up to 40% of untreated patients, and there is an associated risk of decompensated cirrhosis (defined as developing symptomatic complications of liver fibrosis such as jaundice, ascites, variceal hemorrhage, and hepatic encephalopathy) and hepatocellular carcinoma and considered the leading cause of liver cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) globally [19].

Chronic HBV infection accounts for at least 50% of hepatocellular carcinoma cases, and primary liver cancer (approximately 75%–90% of cases are hepatocellular carcinoma) is the second most common cause of death from cancer in the world. Among patients with HBV infection, hepatocellular carcinoma can develop in the absence of cirrhosis; however, hepatocellular carcinoma is typically preceded by cirrhosis in many patients [20].

Prevention of these complications is the major goal of treatment. However, these hard-clinical endpoints may take years or decades to develop and therefore are not suitable to use as endpoints to assess effectiveness of antiviral treatment [19].

Diagnosis

Tests are being developed to quantify levels of intrahepatic HBV replication. These biomarkers are used to identify patients with HBV infection, follow disease progression and response to therapy, and determine efficacy of new agents in clinical trials [21]. Serological markers can be used to diagnose and distinguish between acute and chronic infections.

Commercially available serological tests detect HBV surface antigen (HBsAg seroconversion), HBV envelope antigen (HBeAg seroconversion), HBV surface antibody (anti-HBs), HBV core antibody (anti-HBc), HBV envelope antibody (anti-HBe; [19,20]).

by rapid diagnostic tests (RDTs) in lateral flow, flow through or simple agglutination assays formats. Laboratory-based immunoassays to detect HBsAg include traditional radioimmunoassays (RIA) and enzyme immunoassays (EIA), as well as newer technologies such as electrochemiluminescence immunoassays (ECLIA), microparticle enzyme immunoassays (MEIA) and chemiluminescent microparticle immunoassays (CMIA), which use signal amplification to give quantitative measurements [22].

Which are used to identify patients who have been exposed to hepatitis B virus (HBV), whereas other tests provide information on the level of virus replication, presence of specific variants, and presence of virus reservoirs [21]. Moreover; Using biochemical (normalization of serum alanine aminotransferase [ALT] level), histological (improvement in necroinflammation and/or fibrosis) and virological (undetectable HBV DNA level; [19]), In addition to serum tests, an assessment of the fibrosis and cirrhosis status in patients with chronic HBV infection is also important for disease prognostication, treatment indication and management. An accurate but invasive test of liver disease is liver biopsy, whereas noninvasive tests include transient elastography (to measure liver stiffness; [2]), surrogate markers have been used to detect infection and evaluate effectiveness of therapy [19].

Chronic HBV infection is defined as detection of HBsAg on 2 occasions measured at least 6 months apart. Individuals at risk for HBV infection (populations with 2% prevalence of HBV infection) should be screened with serological tests for the presence of HBsAg, anti-HBs, and anti-HBc. Among individuals who recover from HBV infection, 80 % will develop anti-HBs and all will develop anti-HBc [23]. Among these tests, loss of HBsAg is considered the ideal treatment endpoint because it is strongly associated with sustained HBV DNA suppression and a low rate of complications from CHB including HCC and liver-related death [24]. Unfortunately, HBsAg loss is rarely achieved with current antiviral therapy [13].

With the development of novel antiviral agents to treat CHB, there has been renewed interest in using HBsAg loss as a therapeutic endpoint. However, there has been some debate as to whether HBsAg loss alone or HBsAg loss and development of antibody to HBsAg (anti-HBs) (HBsAg seroconversion) should be the endpoint of therapy [23]. Detection of anti-HBs indicates development of immune control and is believed to be necessary for any definition of “cure” [19].

HBV tests varies worldwide; resource-constrained areas are less likely to have access to tests that measure virus replication or detect variants and have greater reliance on serologic tests [21].

In difficult-to-access populations, point-of-care (POC) tests are important and significant advances have been made in the past few years. POC tests are small devices that use blood or saliva to detect or measure of viral antibodies and/or antigens [25].

The World Health Organization (WHO) has endorsed the use of rapid diagnostic tests for diagnosis of chronic HBV infection [18] but the American Association for the Study of Liver Diseases (AASLD) and European Association for the Study of the Liver (EASL) guidelines do not. The WHO recommends POC tests to improve access and linkage to care and treatment. Only a few rapid diagnostic tests for HBsAg have met WHO qualification criteria (Vikia HBsAg; Biomérieux, Craonne, France; SD BIOLINE HBsAg; Abbott, Chicago, IL; [21]).

Materials and Methods:

Materials and Devices

The materials that were used in this study were listed in the Table 1 and all of devices that utilized in this study were listed in Table 2.

Table 1: The Materials and Tools that Were Used in the Study

Name of the material	Company	Country
Gel tube		
White tube		
Hbs Ag ultra	bioMérieux	France
Micropipette (1000 µL, 200µL)		

Table 2: The Devices that Were Used in the Study

Name of the Device	Company	Country
MINIVIDAS Automated ELISA	bioMérieux	France
Centrifuge		
Refrigerator		
Vortex		

Sample Collection

A total of 40 samples were collected from patients infected with Hbs viral infection who are outpatients to Abu Ghraib General Hospital, Baghdad and Al-Qaim General Hospital in Al-Qaim city and Fallujah Teaching hospital for maternity and children and Many private laboratories in Fallujah city from 15th October 2022 to 2nd March 2023.

The included patients in this study were patients who are infected with Hepatitis B (Hbs) Virus infection from different stages of infection (especially the end stage of infection) or recovered from the infection.

A questionnaire were applied during sample collection to gather the information from patients including: age, Gender, Type of drug, Stage of disease, Time from infection, HBS viral load if present, liver enzymes (ALT, AST, ALP) if present.

Many of those information were excluded because of its none availability for many patients.

The blood samples were collected from each patient using venipuncture and transferred to a gel tube, it were left on the table until completely clotted then centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 5 minutes. A clear serum were obtained from the samples which transferred lastly to a white tube with ensuring of labeling the tubes with all information of the sample and preserved in a refrigerator at -20 °C until using.

Measuring of Hbs Ag Concentration in the Samples of Study Group

HBS Ag Ultra (HBS) is an automated qualitative test for use on the MINIVIDAS instruments for the detection of hepatitis B surface antigen (HBs Ag) in human serum, using the ELFA technique (Enzyme Linked Fluorescent Assay).

Kit components

1. HBS strips (STR)
2. HBS SPRs (Interior of SPRs coated with two monoclonal anti-HBs Ag antibodies).
3. HBS standard (S1), (lyophilized) require construction, Supplemented with inactivated human plasma HBs antigen + preservatives. This material require preparation in 1 mL of sterile distilled water (stand for 20 minutes and mixe with vortex before using).
4. HBS positive control (C1) Ready-to-use.
5. Negative control (C2) Ready-to-use.

Identification and Calibration of the MINIVIDAS device for HbsAg Ultra kit

1. The device were set on MLE barcoding to read the Master lot number of the kit and identify it for the device.
2. The Calibration, using the standard provided in the kit, must be performed upon receipt of a new lot of reagents after the master lot data have been entered. Calibration should then be performed every 14 days.
3. The standard, identified by S1, must be tested in duplicate. The standard value must be within the set RFV "Relative Fluorescence Value" range. Followed by Positive control (C1) and Negative control (C2)
4. All the kit components must reach to room temperature for at least 30 minutes.
5. The test is identified by the "HBS" code on the instrument, The standard must be identified by "S1", and tested in duplicate. the positive control identified as "C1". And negative control identified by C2.
6. Mix the standard, controls and samples using a vortex type mixer.
7. For this test, the calibrator, control, and sample

test portion is 150 µl.

8. Insert the "HBS" SPRs and "HBS" strips into the device.

9. The assay will be completed within approximately 60 to 90 minutes, depending on the protocol selected.

Sample assay

A quantity of 150 µL of the serum sample which left to reach to room temperature were applied to the kit strips and the same instruction of identification of the sample in the device were used the start the program.

Results and Interpretation

The results calculation done according to the equation:

$$i = \text{test value} = \text{patient RFV} / \text{standard RFV}$$

Interpretation of results according to test values is as follows:

Result	Interpretation
$i < 0.10$	Negative
$i > 0.10$	Positive

Statistical Analysis

Using SPSS program (Ver 26), at probability levels (0.05) and (0.01) using means, S.D and chi square. RESULTS:

One of the most important stages that any patient infected with HBs virus aim to reach it is the seroclearance stage when he would be eligible to practice his activities normally as a carrier for the infection. Therefore; this study aim to study the patient characteristics that might be correlate with attaining the seroclearance state including the age, gender, disease stage and specifically the type of drug.

The study results showed that among 30 patients randomly selected with confirmed HBs infection recently, the number of Males (19) is higher than Females (11) and the concentration of HBs Ag is higher in the males (15.170 ± 6.51 ng/ml) than females (14.40 ± 7.66 ng/ml) with no significant differences calculated statistically (P value > 0.05) as shown in Table (4.1) and Figure 3.

The mean of ages in our study was 41.8 ± 13.4 years and the percentage of ages higher than 35 years (30%) was lower than younger patients under 35 years (70%) indicating that most of infected people were younger age groups from our population. The concentrations of HBs Ag in the patients older than 35 years were lower significantly (15.0 ± 6.9 ng/ml ; P value =0.02) than the patients younger than 35 years (15.5 ± 6.9 ng/ml) as indicated in the table 3 without presence of significant correlation between ages and gender (P value = 0.282). Most of the patients that included in our study were patients with end or advanced stage of infection who may receive drug for treatment of not (93.3 %) with a mean ($14.95142857 \pm 6.896200152$ ng/ml) compared with those who were in the initial stages of therapy who represent a low percentage of our study group (6.6 %)

with a mean (19.125 ± 0.005 ng/ml) as indicated in table 3.

Table 3: Show the Characteristics of Patients in the Study Group

Characteristic	No.	Mean of HBs Ag ± SD(ng/ml)
Gender		
Female	11 (39 %)	14.40±7.66*
Male	19 (67%)	15.170±6.51
Ages		
Total Mean ± SD	41.8 + 13.4 years	
	No. (Percentage)	Mean ± S.D
<=35	9 (30%)	15.5 ± 6.9
>35	21 (70%)	15.0 ± 6.9
Stage of infection		Mean ± S.D
First stage	6.6 %	19.125 ± 0.005
Advanced stage	93.3 %	14.9 ± 6.8

Note: * non- significant differences (P value = 0.627)

Most of the patients who were in the end stage of infection were in the agegroup older than 35 years (20) and lesser numbers exist in the age group younger than 35 years (8) with equal distribution of the patients in the firststage between the two age groups as appear in Table 4.

Only 4 patients in our study showed undetectable concentrations of HBs Ag while the highest number (significantly with a P value = 0.03) of the patients showed positive results ranging from (8.08 ng/ml to 20.47 ng/ml)with a mean equal to 17.57 ± 3.4 ng/ml as showed in Table 5.

Figure 3: Correlation between Gender and HBs Ag Concentration in the Study Group

Note: * non- significant differences (P value = 0.627)

Table 4: The Distribution of Study Group According to Age Groups and the Stage of Infection

Age	First stage	End stage	Total
≤ 35	1	8	9
> 35	1	20	21
Total	2	28	30

Table 5. The Distribution of Study Group Patients According to the HBs Ag Result Interpretation and the Means of HBs Ag Concentration Comparison between Both Results

HBs Ag result	No.	Mean ± ST
-ve	4	0.000 ± 0
+ve	26	17.57 ± 3.4* ng/ml

Note: * significant difference (P value = 0.03)

The concentration of HBs Ag in the patients who were in the first stage of infection was higher (19.12 ± 0.007 ng/ml) than the patients in the end stage (14.192±7.02 ng/ml) without significant differences noticed between them (P value =0.07) as showed in Figure 4. The highest number of patients in our study did not receive any type of treatment during the period of sample collection (with no confirmation if they receive any drug recently or not) were 13 patients followed by Tenofovir and Entecavir (7 and 6 sequentially) and the least number were patients who receive adefovir (3 patients) followed by lamivudine (1 patient only). There is non-significant difference between number of males or females with the selecting a specific type of drug despite ((P value = 0.9), the results appear in Table 6.

Figure 4: Correlation between Disease Stage and HBs Ag Concentrations in Study Group

Note: * Non significant differences (p value = 0.07)

All of the patients who were in the first stage of infection and most of the patients in the end stage did not receive any type of treatment (2 and 12 patients respectively) as appear in Table 7 with presence of

Significant differences between the drug type and disease stage (P value < 0.05)

Moreover; all the patients who showed negative results for HBs Ag were patients who receive Tenofovir drug (Significantly with P value = 0.02) while all the rest of patients showed positive results for the test as appear in Table 8.

The most effective drug for reducing HBs Ag concentration in the patients was Tenofovir (8.63 ± 0.400083 ng/ml) followed by Entecavir (16.4775± 1.78169 ng/ml) then patients with no drug and lamivudine (18.00231± 4.861144 and 18.92 ± 0.0 respectively) and the least effect appear in Adefovir (20.12 ± 8.461187 ng/ml) as indicated in table 9.

Table 6: Distribution of Patient Study Group According to Their Gender and Type of Drug that They Receive

Gender	No drug	Tenofovir	Entecavir	adefovir	lamivudine	total
Male	7	5	4	2	1	19
Female	6	2	2	1	0	11
Total	13	7	6	3	1	30

Note: * non-significant differences (P value = 0.9)

Table7: Distribution of Study Group According to the Disease Stage and the Correlation with Type of Drug

Drug types	First	End	total
No drug	2	11	13
Tenofovir	0	7	7
Entecavir	0	6	6
Adefovir	0	3	3
lamivudine	0	1	1
Total	2	28	30

Table 8: The Distribution of Positive and Negative Results According to the Type of Drug that the Patients Receive

Drug types	-ve	+ve	total
No drug	0	13	13
Tenofovir	4	3	7
Entecavir	0	6	6
Adefovir	0	3	3
lamivudine	0	1	
Total	4	26	30

Note: * Significant difference (P value = 0.02)

Table 9: The Mean and S.D Values of HBs Ag in Different Types of Drugs and Distributed According to Stage of Infection

Drug types	Mean S.D		Stage of infection	
			First	End stage
No drug	18.002±4.8		19.125 ± 0.005	17.7 ± 0.4
Tenofovir	8.63 ± 0.4		0	8.63±0.4
Entecavir	16.4775 ± 1.78		0	16.4 ± 1.7
Adefovir	20.12 ± 8.46		0	20.12 ± 8.46
lamivudine	18.92 ± 0.0	±	0	18.9 ± 0.0
Total	15.2	6.74	19.125 ± 0.005	14.9 ± 6.8

Conclusion

By comparing concentrations of HBsAg between the first and end stage of infection with the type of drug, the patients in first stage of infection receive no drug with a mean (19.125 ± 0.005 ng/ml) of HBs Ag and the end stage was (17.79818 ± 0.400083 ng/ml) without difference of other types of drugs from the recent values because of absence of patients who receive any drug in the first stage of infection. As in table 9.

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